

CrossReality

1. General Information

Performance Title: CrossReality

Main Contact: Kaiqing Huang

Additional Performers: Boxiong Zhao、 Chu Zhang、 Kaiqing Huang、 Wangyu Ping、 Botao (Amber) Hu

Performance Type: concert

2. Abstract

The performance, based on the interconnection between virtual and real media, primarily explores the mutual influence relationship between architectural spaces and individuals or groups. The presence of individuals in architectural spaces is not merely static but involves dynamic shaping of the spatial environment. The characteristics and changes in architectural environments directly affect the capabilities and perceptual experiences of individuals, forming a bidirectional interactive relationship. Furthermore, the architecture itself, as a dynamic element, deeply influences the perceptions, behaviors, and emotional states of individuals through its structure, design, and functionality. This influence may leave lasting traces on individuals' cognition and emotional levels.

In multi-person environments, interactions among different individuals will generate more complex dynamics in the spatial context. The collective behaviors and relationships among multiple individuals will shape the collective characteristics of architectural spaces, thereby affecting the overall atmosphere and energy of the space. Interactions between individuals also to some extent regulate the process of architectural space changes, creating a more random and multi-layered spatial atmosphere.

Throughout the performance, performers gradually explore and visualize the bidirectional shaping relationship between architectural spaces and individuals or groups. They investigate the connections between people and people, and people and spaces through bodily actions and group interaction experiments. Through this exploration, they derive the logic of performance and interaction, which is driven by the energy of architectural spaces, leading to spontaneous improvisations with other performers. The performance aims to delve into and visualize the bidirectional shaping relationship between architectural spaces and individuals or groups, discussing its extension in the context of artistic performances.

The visual form of the performance demonstrates the concept of transformation. Within the context of architectural spaces, interactions between individuals and groups lead to distortions in the spatial environment and energy of architectural spaces. The architectural environment dynamically shapes the emotions and movements of individuals and collectives in space and time. In

this context, the concept of transformation can be understood as the transformation of the spatiotemporal and energetic coordinate systems within architectural spaces, used to simulate the influence of architectural spaces on the trajectories of individual and group movements. Through this approach, the performers and audience are guided to engage in new reflections on multimedia cross-reality and the energy and space of architectural environments.

The performance showcases various technologies, including ARKit, Unity control, Netcode network communication, OCS communication technology, and real-time music programming technology based on Max and SonicPi. It involves transmitting the position information of performers wearing AR devices in real-time to the main host computer controlling Unity, creating the effect of a "energy sphere" dynamically surrounding multiple performers in virtual scenes. When multiple performers are in specific positions, the "energy sphere" continuously traverses physical simulated architectural structures and projection visuals in real-world AR. As the "energy sphere" moves, the "architectural domain lines" in AR are dynamically stretched, attracted, and impacted, influenced by the physical movements of performers, which in turn affect virtual AR and projection visuals, blurring the boundaries between reality and virtuality. Additionally, real-time programming enables real-time adjustments and changes in screen amplitude, content presentation, and sound output, enhancing the spontaneity and creativity of the performance, resulting in a unique stage effect for each group of performers.

3. Video and/or Audio Material

<https://youtu.be/nFS2MMFvLv4>

4. Program Note

The performance is centered around completely bridging the boundary between virtual and reality, enabling real-time AR interaction, real-time music programming interaction, and real-time projection interaction. Each performer is a direct creator of AR and music content, while the projection content is interactively presented in real-time through AR and music content. This non-regular, non-predefined performance will bring about unexpected cross-reality real-time audio-visual interactive performances.

5. Artist(s) Biography

Resonator, our team is led by Professors Tongzhou Yu, Yongru Lu, and Botao Hu from the School of Innovative Design at the China Academy of Art, is formed with a focus on the comprehensive exploration of spatial computing. Leveraging artificial intelligence, mixed reality, virtual reality, laser radar sensors, and game development, we have investigated cross-device spatiotemporal synchronization over the past year. Our research resulted in the seamless integration of traditional 3D displays, augmented reality, and real-time music programming in a multidimensional space. This innovative solution has successfully been applied in art exhibitions and commercial collaborations across multiple locations.

Boxiong Zhao, currently residing in Hangzhou, is a visual artist and creative programmer affiliated with the China Academy of Art. With a background in visual design, he has been actively engaged in creating visual art through software and coding in recent years. His practice spans live performances, videos, digital media, and installations, exploring abstract narratives. By combining computer graphics (CG) and augmented reality (AR), he crafts captivating digital landscapes. Collaborating with musicians to integrate real-time coding and virtual visuals, his works have been exhibited at events such as the Jin Daiqiang Design Award, China Digital Art Exhibition (CDSA), and the Boiling Bronze Art Festival. Additionally, he is part of the Lightning Institute's Art Support Program, contributing to artistic creation.

Chu Zhang is an undergraduate student at the School of Innovation Design, China Academy of Art, and serves as the lead vocalist for the "New Youth Band." His academic focus lies in Digital Media Art and AR Development, with a primary research interest in the application of sound interaction in AR environments and the emotional impact of sound within multimedia contexts. Additionally, he explores the utilization of music for therapeutic purposes and emotional resonance. In the realm of digital media art performances, Zhang Chu is experimenting with incorporating live coding, using SonicPi, Max/MSP, and Unity for real-time music synthesis and interaction with body movements. Through such exploration, he aims to discover the synergy between the soul and the body, pushing the boundaries of new territories at the intersection of performance and music.

Kaiqing Huang is currently pursuing studies at the Institute of Media and Interaction in the School of Innovation Design at the China Academy of Art, specializing in the intersection of art and technology. His works span across digital film, interactive installations, programming interactions, virtual reality, and augmented reality art. He focuses on exploring the expansiveness of multimedia and cross-media art. Drawing inspiration not only from the art industry and academia but also from the fields of biology, medicine, and anthropology, Huang Kaiqing believes that such interdisciplinary integration provides art with greater creativity and possibilities in presentation.

Wangyu Ping, a current undergrad at the China Academy of Art majoring in Digital Media Art, seamlessly blends academic pursuits with practical involvement. Recipient of consecutive school scholarships, her exhibited works showcase her dedication. Collaborating with China Aerospace Eighth Academy and various companies, she contributed to the "2023 New Art and Science Future Vision" exhibition. Currently delving into cross-device temporal synchronization, she holds a strong interest in cutting-edge tech like AI and VR. Eager to share her academic insights and research on your platform, Ping aims to contribute to the convergence of art, technology, and academia.

Botao (Amber) Hu is a spatial computing researcher, creative technologist, and media artist. He is the founder of Holo Interactive, a spatial computing lab. His primary focus lies in XR design theory, with a particular emphasis on co-located multiplayer AR and Cross-Reality. With expertise in AI, XR, ZKML, robotics, game studies, media theory, and visual design, he has collaborated with renowned companies such as Apple, Twitter, DJI, Google, Microsoft,

Pinterest, and thatgamecompany. His works have been featured at top conferences like SIGGRAPH, WWW, CHI, SXSW, TEDx, and received awards including CHI Best Interactivity, Red Dot Design Award, Webby Awards, and Core77 Design Award. He is notably the inventor of HoloKit, an open-source AR headset highly regarded by esteemed research institutions like MIT Media Lab, NYU ITP, Stanford, and Harvard for their mixed reality education and research initiatives. He holds a bachelor's degree in computer science from Tsinghua University and a master's degree in AI from Stanford University.

6. Revision

We will replace the three electronic screens with top-down projections, and add six white physical booths of different sizes in this area for performances. The reference size of the booths is 100*40*50cm, 140* 30*30cm, 40*30*50cm, 70*40*40cm, 60*60*50cm, 70*50*40cm, the booth size can be adjusted at will according to the actual situation. Expression, abandoning the visual presentation of the last two acts.